

NODES – Nord Ovest Digitale e Sostenibile

FLAGSHIP PROJECT GRIP

SPOKE 2 –GREEN TECHNOLOGIES AND SUSTAINABLE INDUSTRIES

DELIVERABLE D2.1: Data about chemical and nutritional profiling of raw wastes and by products

REPORTING PERIOD	
Period covered:	from M1 to M14
Periodic report date and version:	from M1 to M14
Deliverable D2.1 Responsible	UPO, Marco Arlorio
RM2 Responsible	UPO, Marco Arlorio

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Glossary

	Definition
Hub Coordinator (HC)	The Hub Coordinator represents the single point of contact for the implementation of the innovation ecosystem towards the MUR. It carries out the management and coordination activities of the innovation ecosystem, receives the fundings, verifies, and transmits to the MUR the reporting of the activities carried out by the Spoke and their affiliates.
National Recovery and Resilience Plan (NRRP)	This document uses the Italian acronym for the NRRP, which is PNRR (Piano Nazionale della Ripresa e Resilienza)
Research Program Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the overall scientific contents of the NODES project. The NODES will appoint the Research Program Manager. It refers to "Responsabile del Programma di Ricerca" in the MUR's Call of proposal for "Ecosistemi di Innovazione"
NODES' Research and innovation program	NODES' Research and Innovation program is articulated in specific programs for each Spoke, with the aim to promote and support applied research on topics consistent with the Intelligent Specialization Strategy, with the guidelines of the 2021-2027 partnership agreement scheme, with regional operational plans and regional and national research and innovation priorities. Although NODES' Spokes are concentrated on different themes, they will organize their activities and actions within a common framework – NODES' Booster Methodology
Spoke Coordinator	The University in charge of coordinating the Spoke's ecosystem. It refers to "Spoke" in the MUR's Call of proposal for "Ecosistemi di Innovazione"
Spoke Data Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the monitoring and management of data generated at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Data Manager.
Spoke Partner	The entity associated to the Spoke Coordinator. It can be an Innovation Cluster, Competence Center, Research Center related to the Spoke's ecosystem and contributes to achieve objectives and impact under the Spoke' leadership and management. It refers to "soggetti affiliati" in the MUR's Call of proposal for "Ecosistemi di Innovazione".
Spoke Project manager	The person who will be the responsible for the management, coordination and progress of the project at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Project Manager.
Spoke research and innovation program	NODES' Research and Innovation program is articulated in specific programs for each Spokes. The spoke will leverage a consolidated collaboration with leading private and public companies and will focus the applied research activity on technological domains and applications that can favour the integration of SMEs into new value chains.
Spoke Scientific and Technical Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the overall scientific contents of the project at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Scientific and Technical Manager.
Spoke Stakeholders Committee (SC)	Consultation structure formed by relevant stakeholders (Government, universities, companies, civil society, third sector, etc.)
Spoke Thematic	General target focus and domain of the Spoke research.
Spoke Topics	Specific areas/lines of development within the Spoke.
Spoke Work Package Leader	At the Spoke level, Work Packages (WPs) will be organized by WP leaders, who will be responsible for performance evaluation and reporting.
Flagship Project	Main research project at the Spoke level with the goal of prototyping, testing, demonstrating the research activities towards higher TRLs.

List of Deliverables

D. No	Name	Lead Beneficiary	Type	Dissemination Level	Due Date	New Due Date (if delay)	Delivery Date (actual)
[number]	[name]	[short name]	[R — Document, report] [DEM — Demonstrator, pilot, prototype] [DEC — Websites, patent filings, videos, etc] [DATA — data sets, microdata, etc] [DMP — Data Management Plan] [ETHICS] [SECURITY] [OTHER]	[PU — Public] [SENSITIVE] [R] [C] [S]	[month number]	[dd/mm/yyyy]	[dd/mm/yyyy]
D2.1	Data about chemical and nutritional profilin	UPO	R	PU	M14		18/04/2024

	g of raw wastes and by products						
D2.2.1	On line lab-scale technical multi-device for waste processing*	<i>UPO</i>	Other (material)	PU	M18 (June)		
D2.2.2	Delivery of protocols (lab-scale) ready to scale-up the production of new high-value material (in collaboration with Companies)	<i>UPO</i>	R	PU	M22		
D2.3.1	New data about valorized matrices characterization and high value products	<i>UPO</i>	R	PU	M28		

D2.3.2	New characterized ingredients/materials for food, nutraceuticals, pharmaceutical and cosmetic applications	<i>UPO</i>	Other (material)	PU	M30		
D2.4.1	New data about sustainable production of new materials from biomass	<i>UPO</i>	R	PU	M24		
D2.4.2	New characterized materials from biomass	<i>UPO</i>	Other (material)	PU	M30		
D2.5.2	Porous sorbents from biomass valorization	<i>UPO</i>	Other (material)	PU	M30		
D2.6.1	New material produced at pilot scale ready to the formulation or co-	<i>UPO</i>	Other (material)	PU	M32		

	formulation (in collaboration with Companies)						
D2.6.2	New well characterized process and formulated pilot-products (in collaboration with Companies)	<i>UPO</i>	R/Other (Material)	PU	M32		
D2.7	Report on the adsorption and/or catalytic performances of porous solids derived from biomass valorization and non-recyclable plastic wastes	<i>UPO</i>	R	PU	M32		

A) INTRODUCTION

The partners involved in the WP2 (UNITO; POLITO; UPO; UNIPV; ENVIPARK; *Design and set-up of customized combined processes for biomasses processing and valorization*; M8-M30) identified first a list of potential technologies useful to process and up-cycle the raw materials (waste, by-products from different origin, organic material) selected as starting point for the identification of performing materials useful to scale up green processes, so obtaining high value compounds/ingredients and new materials.

The list of the main technologies available is reported in point D.

The partial (or complete) characterization of the raw matrices, as well as some preliminary results related to some interesting compounds, is also reported and listed. These activities allowed the requested knowledge useful to select the best performing materials and the best performing processes in terms of utility, novelty, feasibility and yield.

A peculiar attention regarding the selection has been paid on the comparison with common process based on “non-green” technologies”, focusing on the reduction of the impact at environmental level.

B) ROLE OF PARTNERS

The role of partners was distributed depending on the i) matrix availability and ii) the facilities availability.

More particularly, Environment Park, UPO, UNITO, POLITO, ENVIPARK and UNIPV worked in synergy in order to identify the raw material and to explore more solutions as possible on different matrices, testing some technologies and reporting the best performing capacity of up-cycling, as well as the best potential for the future scale-up at pilot level.

The first role of the Partners was related to the identification of the sources (producers) of the raw material to be characterized and processed. A preliminary analysis of availability (scale of production of materials) was made. Moreover, a significant quantity for each material was provided; during the first step, a lab scale of sampling was considered. A key parameter for providing of the materials to all the Partners was the idea to recover the material in the geographical zone interested by NODES Project, so reducing the potential logistic cost and thinking in terms of “short chain” valorization. Each partners shared technological and analytical competences and skills, providing

complementary knowledge and ensuring the feasibility of the research activity.

The raw materials were characterized and some preliminary green approach were done, in order to test the potential of the thereof.

C) EXPLANATION OF THE WORK CARRIED OUT AND OVERVIEW OF THE PROGRESS

The overall work was planned in three phases:

1. *Identification of the materials and identification of the needs*
2. *Identification and selection of the technological green/bio-based processes useful to process, valorize and up-cycle the identified raw materials and*
3. *characterization and valorization of the raw matrices.*

1. The identification of the raw materials was done considering the main food chains present in the NODES area. Waste, by products and organic material were considered (e.g. plant material from fruit cold pressing; residues post processing like spent coffee; waste from hazelnut processing; by-products from cocoa hulls and soy; whey and other milk-related materials, ...), as reported in detail in M2.1.
2. A list of green and bio-based (especially solvent free) technologies were considered both for extract/fractionate and valorize the raw materials. The complete list of available facilities/technologies is reported below (classified in term of availability at each single Partner):

Envipark

In particular, steam explosion and/or enzymatic hydrolysis were identified for the extraction phase, followed by filter pressing and/or centrifugation and membrane filtration for the purification and concentration of the molecules.

Green Chemistry Area of Envipark is equipped with the following facilities:

- **STEAM EXPLOSION**

The steam explosion process is based on the use of saturated or slightly supersaturated steam at pressure rising up to 26 bar with the related equilibrium temperature of around 227°C. The biomass to be treated gets in contact with vapor for the process defined timing (resulting from the selected severity of the process). After this time, the material is immediately expanded

into an atmospheric pressure vessel. The sudden reduction of pressure causes a violent vapor expansion, resulting in the breaking up of the chemical linkages in the treated material. The steam explosion reactor consists of two vessels, one for the pressurization of the biomass (R101) and the other for the following expansion (V101) of the biomass at atmospheric pressure (vessel directly connected to the atmosphere with a funnel).

- ENZYMATIC HYDROLYSIS

The enzymatic hydrolysis reactor is a vertical glass cylindrical vessel (total volume of 5 l) equipped with pH and temperature probes that ensure very precise control of the parameters of the reactor. Since enzymatic or biological reactions are usually carried out at moderate temperatures, temperature control must be guaranteed.

- MULTI-PURPOSE CENTRIFUGE MODULE

The multi-purpose centrifuge module is used to clarify a liquid from solids as well as separating two liquid phases. It is a mobile separation unit consisting of a stainless steel skid fitted with a separator and all other safety equipment. Separation takes place inside a rotating bowl: the feed is introduced to the rotating centrifuge bowl from the top via a stationary inlet pipe, and is accelerated in the distributor, before entering the disc stack. The separation of liquid-solids takes place between the discs, with the liquid phase moving through the disc stack to the centre and is led to the paring chamber, where it is pumped out of the rotor through a built-in paring disc. The solids are collected in the periphery, from where it is discharged intermittently into the solids collecting cover.

- MEMBRANES FILTRATION SMALL PLANT

The tangential filtration machine can install one housing for ceramic membranes and one housing for wound spiral membranes. The plant can perform filtration tests with microfiltration, ultrafiltration, nanofiltration and reverse osmosis membranes.

The machine is completely manual and technically structured with innovative measures compared to normal separation technologies, to obtain higher levels of performance in terms of quality and quantity. The system (600 x 700 x 700 mm) is equipped with one spiral polymer membrane module wound and operates up to a maximum pressure of about 70.0 bar.

- SEPARATION PLANT BASED ON PNEUMATIC PRESS

The plant enables solid/liquid separation through a 20-liter pneumatic press with a cloth filter.

The press consists of a membrane that swells due to the input of compressed air and pushes the suspension against the walls of the perforated cage. The liquid part is therefore separated and collects at the base of the press, while the solid part remains inside the cloth filter and can be similarly recovered.

UPO

Considering the availability of the technologies and based on the work related to the preliminary treatment of the selected raw matrices (plant and animal waste/by products), UPO can contribute to the activity of up-cycling with:

- ENZYME DRIVEN-HYDROLYSIS / FERMENTATION (liquid state)

A bioreactor (1.5 l) is available both for i) enzyme-driven hydrolysis and ii) fermentation using microorganisms (principally bacteria and yeast). A complete station for the monitoring and control of fermentation (allowing the monitoring of temperature, pH, oxygen) complete the bioreactor system. A customized chamber of treatment permits the on-line application of a US probe in order to pre-treat (or post-treat) the material.

- ULTRASOUNDS

An high-power ultrasounds probe (and relative US generator) is available for the extraction intensification. The probe can be also used in a special chamber also in combination with the bioreactor (lab scale).

- ULTRAFILTRATION (lab-scale and pilot-scale)

Lab-scale device for UF, useful to concentrate small volumes of samples (planar organic membranes; 0.5 l max volume) is available for the set-up of methods.

A pilot scale (designed to use polysulphone membranes) coupled with pump is also available, permitting to concentrate and fractionate (retentate, permeate) volumes up to 15-30 liters.

- CROMATOGRAPHY COLOUM AND ROTOVAPOR SYSTEMS

Different preparative chromatography columns are available for extraction/separation/clean-up of liquid extracts in water or organic solvents. A relative high-volume rotavapor system is available for the reduction of the volume as well as to remove solvents.

- SUB-CRITICAL WATER (incoming plant)

Sub-critical water (incoming customized plant) will be explored in the next future (particularly concerning the scale-up of the process for small molecules of high added value) depending on the capacity to extract molecules that in usual conditions (T, pressure, water extraction) are insoluble in water, improving the capacity to recover bioactive compounds in a “green” manner. This plant (under construction) is required in the work related to the Academic POC “GREEN.VAL.” (UPO).

Moreover, the following devices can be used to formulate the liquid extract producing powders with properties:

- SPRAY DRYER

Spray drying is one of the most used microencapsulation methods. In general, a solution, a dispersion or an emulsion, composed of the active substance to be encapsulated and one or more carrier materials, is nebulized in the drying chamber of the equipment (spray dryer). The small droplets are immediately subjected to a hot air stream responsible for the instantaneous solvent evaporation. The active substance is thus entrapped in an inert support and the obtained product is a fine powder.

The Spray dryer Buchi available at UPO is characterized by an evaporative capacity (water) of 1 kg/hours, with a max inlet temperature of 220 °C.

- LYOPHILIZER

Freeze drying is a process used to remove the water present in a sample by sublimation. It is typically used to preserve materials, with the goal of extending their shelf life. The sample was frozen, then the pressure was reduced and heat was added to allow the frozen water in the material to change directly to a vapor state (sublimate). This approach, in combination with spray-drying, is useful to formulate and stabilize some final products extracted and valorised using the previously described technologies.

The system available at UPO is a lab-scale and pilot freeze-drying unit able to freeze dry liquids and solids in vials, trays or other glass containers.

Condenser capacity: 5 kg

Condenser temperature: -85 °C

Condenser performance: 4 kg/24 h

Unit dimensions: 1267 x 860 x 650 mm

Plates number: 3

Plates dimensions: 225 x 300 mm.

A complete set of analytical devices complete the set-up of the UPO's lab (HPLC-DAD, LC-MS, GC-FID, GC-MS, GCxGC-TOF, GC-IMS, Lab-on-chip micro-electrophoresis, Fibertec system, other minor facilities)

POLITO

POLITO could aid in the valorization of selected waste through sub-critical extractions, ultrasonic, microwave, or enzymatic processes, utilizing laboratory-scale equipment, particularly employing the following apparatuses:

- ENZYME DRIVEN-HYDROLYSIS / FERMENTATION (liquid state)

Three bioreactors, sized at 2 liters and 10 liters respectively, are accessible for both enzyme-mediated hydrolysis and fermentation employing microorganisms, predominantly bacteria and yeast. Additionally, a comprehensive station for monitoring and controlling fermentation, facilitating oversight of temperature, pH, and oxygen levels, complements the bioreactor setup.

- ULTRASOUNDS

A high-power ultrasound probe, along with its corresponding US generator, is at disposal to enhance extraction processes.

- SUB-CRITICAL WATER

A one-liter small-scale supercritical water reactor facilitates high-temperature, high-pressure chemical reactions, exploiting water's unique properties in a state between gas and liquid. It serves various applications such as synthesis, biofuel production, and extraction of bioactive compounds from plants or organisms. It's ideal for laboratory research and pilot process development in green chemistry, biotechnology, and renewable resource valorization.

- MICROVAWE

100 ml microwave reactors for extractions streamline the extraction process using microwave energy, enabling efficient extraction of desired compounds from raw materials. Ideal for small-scale experiments and rapid extraction procedures in research settings.

Additionally, we have various tools for preparation and characterization, including rotovapors, incubators, HPLC with DAD and RID detectors, GC-MS and GC-FID systems, ATR-IR, IR, UV, and others.

UNITO

The contribute of UNITO is mainly oriented to laboratory scale processes and the characterization of the products. Most useful instrumentations and techniques are:

- MICROVAWE

Some reactors for extraction processes by microwave energy are available.

- ULTRAFILTRATION

Lab-scale ultrafiltration systems are available at different cut-off level. A pilot plant for testing of ultrafiltration membranes is planned to be installed soon.

- ULTRASOUNDS

An US generator and relative ultrasound probe to facilitate extraction processes is available.

- FLOW CHEMISTRY SYSTEM

A modular flow chemistry system with different reactors for synthesis and partial separation of extracts was recently acquired. With this instrument, matrices in solution can be exposed to various processes, such as irradiation with different wavelengths, or treatments at different temperature, pH values and solvents.

Moreover, a complete characterization of the matrices could be supported by the extensive use of UNITO instrumentation for analyses in solution (various instruments for chromatographic separation and analysis methods, in particular by high resolution mass spectrometry) and in solid state (IR and Raman spectroscopies, surface analysis, thermogravimetric and calorimetric analysis, morphological analysis by electron microscopy techniques, etc.).

3. A list of characterized matrices (with some example of valorization and up-cycling) is reported below. Different matrices were considered and each Partner characterized the same applying a single methods as well as combined methods, in order to preliminary test the combination of the most performing matrices, object of the scale-up of the selected matrices/processes during the next months.

Each material is detailed considering a) the description and origin of the matrix; b) the potential processing considered for each matrix and c) the main outcomes, in

terms of characterization and isolation/production of ingredients/molecules/materials.

ENVIPARK

Hazelnut shells and skins

a) Food waste/by-product: Hazelnuts are one of the most widely consumed nuts, but their production creates large quantities of by-products, mainly shells that account for about 42% of the total biomass. The nut processing industries generate many by-products that can be exploited as raw materials for new processes. Hazelnut shells have the potential as a source of antioxidant compounds with a commercial interest in the cosmetic, nutraceutical, pharmaceutical, food supplement, medical device, fertilizer and food industries. The composition of the different parts (leaves, husk, skin, fruit) differs in the type and quantity of functional substances and represents an interesting source of other substances with high added value. The antioxidant activity of these by-products is associated with the presence of phenolic compounds responsible for a broad spectrum of bioactivity, including antioxidant, anti-allergic or antimicrobial effects.

b) Processing considered for the matrix: Based on the results obtained downstream of the physicochemical characterization of hazelnut processing wastes and the data evaluated in the literature, the following are identified as optimal extraction protocols for compounds of interest for agricultural applications (biostimulates for agriculture): steam explosion processes in combination with enzymatic hydrolysis that can generate hydrolysates rich in functional substances. In addition processes to remove the solid fraction from the hydrolysates may also be required for subsequent use in the field.

c) Outcome: the characterisation of hazelnut shells and skins as received was carried out to identify the compounds present and their concentration. The parameters that were analysed are listed in the table below, with the method used for the determination and the unit of measurement. UHPLC-MS MS analysis data are expressed in $\mu\text{g/g}$, while total polyphenol data (Folin Ciocalteu reaction, expressed as catechin) are expressed in mg/g .

		Phenols LC-MS/MS																		
		p-hydroxybenzoic acid	vanillin	vanillic acid	gallic acid	protocatechuic acid	methyl gallate	Ellagic acid	p-coumaric acid	ferulic acid	t-coumaric acid	t-resveratrol	t-piceide	Phlorizin	luteolin	Luteolin-7-O-Glc	Apigenin-7-glc	naringenin	catechin	epicatechin
		µg/g	µg/g	µg/g	µg/g	µg/g	µg/g	µg/g	µg/g	µg/g	µg/g	µg/g	µg/g	µg/g	µg/g	µg/g	µg/g	µg/g	µg/g	µg/g
Hazelnut shells	Scoiattolo rosso	0,18	0,69	0,43	11,39	12,83	0,02	1,80	0,27	0,14	0,15	n.d.	0,09	2,20	0,02	n.d.	0,02	0,04	8,88	1,72
Hazelnut skins	Scoiattolo rosso	0,25	0,03	0,12	16,94	22,13	0,39	1,70	0,33	0,33	0,72	0,54	3,99	22,80	0,11	1,07	0,08	0,15	120,50	33,58
hazelnut shells	Tastelanghe	1,30	0,34	0,60	26,06	30,19	0,11	4,80	0,50	0,13	0,23	0,09	2,09	13,91	0,03	1,02	0,12	0,62	134,09	34,87
hazelnut shells	Greenhas	1,81	0,44	0,87	57,29	166,55	0,22	3,44	0,58	0,08	3,14	0,64	1,73	4,74	0,17	0,66	0,00	0,80	56,85	11,88

		Phenols LC-MS/MS																			
		epigallocatechin	gallo catechin	catechin gallate	gallo catechin gallate	epigallocatechin gallate	epicatechin gallate	Procyanidin B1	procyanidin B2 + B4	procyanidin B3	kaempferol	quercetin	taxifolin	isorhamnetin	myricetin	laricitrin	Quercetin-3-Rha	myricitrin	rutin	isorhamnetin-3-rutinoside	arbutin
		µg/g	µg/g	µg/g	µg/g	µg/g	µg/g	µg/g	µg/g	µg/g	µg/g	µg/g	µg/g	µg/g	µg/g	µg/g	µg/g	µg/g	µg/g	µg/g	µg/g
Hazelnut shells	Scoiattolo rosso	0,08	1,13	0,82	1,04	0,55	0,63	3,27	7,81	11,96	0,05	0,07	0,14	0,01	0,09	n.d.	0,17	0,57	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.
Hazelnut skins	Scoiattolo rosso	3,81	3,30	9,96	1,99	3,56	24,85	41,65	145,58	51,12	0,13	0,96	0,37	0,01	0,67	0,06	8,98	3,88	0,26	0,25	1,57
hazelnut shells	Tastelanghe	2,73	6,60	9,45	0,46	3,72	50,41	54,00	120,73	154,56	0,07	1,43	0,25	0,02	0,76	0,18	6,19	4,99	0,40	0,46	1,92
hazelnut shells	Greenhas	1,08	2,45	2,514	0,59	2,09	34,57	32,53	64,16	122,91	0,18	3,05	0,32	0,01	0,43	0,41	7,25	0,57	0,99	0,93	0,86

		TP
		Total phenols Folin-Ciocalteu (as catechin)
		mg/g
Hazelnut shells	Scoiattolo rosso	8,29
Hazelnut skins	Scoiattolo rosso	87,13
hazelnut shells	Tastelanghe	96,08
hazelnut shells	Greenhas	78,47

As can be seen from the tables above, hazelnuts skins are rich in total polyphenols and has higher concentrations of catechin and procyanidin B3 in particular,

Apple pomace

a) Food waste/by-product: Residues from the processing of fruit and vegetables are generally considered an excellent source of bioactive compounds and, in particular, the waste streams obtained from apple processing (peels and cores) are characterised by having a high antioxidant capacity and a high polyphenol content. Polyphenols comprise a wide and diverse range of organic compounds produced by the secondary metabolism of organisms belonging to the plant kingdom. These chemical compounds, with very simple (phenolic acids) or highly complex chemical structures (flavonoids, stilbenes, lignans and tannins), have an important antioxidant action by counteracting the effects of free radicals responsible for oxidative stress. In apples, for example, the profile of phenolic compounds depends on the cultivar analysed. However, usually the most represented class of polyphenols is always flavanols (71-90 %), while the other identified classes are cinnamic acid derivatives (4-18 %), flavonols (1-11 %), dihydrocalcones (2-6 %), and anthocyanins (1-3 %).

b) Processing considered for the matrix: Apple pomace waste from fruit juice production can be effectively treated with steam explosion processes to obtain hydrolysates that can be used (after concentration and/or bacteriological stabilization) as an active ingredient in the formulation of functional cosmetics. The results obtained from the analyses carried out on the samples after pre-treatment with steam explosion, in fact, generally show a good extraction of antioxidants and total polyphenols (expressed as catechin), in particular the release of

- p-cumaric acid;
- cyanidin-3 galactoside;
- phloridzin;
- quercetin;
- rutin.

With regard to yields versus process severity, the best results were obtained in tests under process severity conditions of approximately 2300 min, specifically

considering the concentrations of phloresin, total flavonoids, total polyphenols, cyanidin-3 galactoside and quercetin. Phloresin appears to be present, however, in all samples treated in different process conditions.

c) Outcome: The characterisation of the apple pomace as received was carried out to identify the compounds present and their concentration. The parameters that were analysed are listed in the table below, with the method used for the determination and the unit of measurement.

Parameter	Method
CAFFEIC ACID (mg/kg)	Caffeic acid-HPLC-MS-mg/kg
CHLOROGENIC ACID (mg/kg)	Chlorogenic acid-HPLC-MS-mg/kg
GALLIC ACID (mg/kg)	Gallic acid-HPLC-MS-mg/kg
M-COUMARIC ACID / O-CUMARIC ACID (expressed as p-coumaric acid) (mg/kg)	O-coumaric acid - HPLC-MS-mg/kg
P-CUMARIC ACID (mg/kg)	P-coumaric acid-HPLC-MS-mg/kg
CATECHIN (mg/kg)	Catechin-HPLC-HQOMS-mg/kg
CYANIDIN 3-ARABINOSIDE (mg/kg)	Cy-3-Arab-EST/HPLC-UV/VIS-mg/kg MV-3-GLC chloride
CYANIDIN 3-GALACTOSIDE (mg/kg)	Cy-3-Gal-EST/HPLC-UV/VIS-mg/kg MV-3-GLC chloride

DIOSMINE (mg/kg)	Dioxin-HPLC-MS-mg/kg
EPICATECHIN (mg/kg)	Epicatechin-HPLC-HQOMS-mg/kg
EXPERIDIN (mg/kg)	Hexperidine-HPLC-MS-mg/kg
FLAVONOIDS TOTALS (as (+)-catechin) (mg/kg)	Flavonoids Total Fna-SPE/SPET- mg/kg(+)-catechin
FLORETIN (mg/kg)	Floretin-HPLC-HQOMS-mg/kg
FLORIZINE (mg/kg)	Phloridzin-HPLC-HQOMS-mg/kg

NARINGINE (mg/kg)	Naringin-HPLC-MS-mg/kg
POLYPHENOLS TOTALS (as (+)-catechin) (mg/kg)	Polyphenols Total-SPEC18/SPET- mg/kg(+)-catechin
QUERCETIN (mg/kg)	Quercetin-HPLC-HQOMS-mg/kg
RUTIN (mg/kg)	Rutin-HPLC/HQOMS-mg/kg
TROXERUTIN (mg/kg)	Troxerutin-HPLC/HQOMS-mg/kg
Loss through drying at 100-105 °C (%)	Loss on drying-%
DELPHINIDIN MONOGLUCOSIDE	Dp-3-Glc-EST/HPLC-UV/VIS- mg/kg MV- 3-GLC chloride

(mg/kg)	
MYRICETIN (mg/kg)	Myricetin- HYDROLISIS ACID/HPLC-UV- mg/kg myricetin
CYANIDIN MONOGLUCOSID E (mg/kg) 3-	Cy-3-Glc-EST/HPLC-UV/VIS- mg/kg MV- 3-GLC chloride
QUERCETIN (mg/kg)	Quercetin- HYDROLISIS ACID/HPLA-UV- mg/kg quercetin
LARICITRINE (mg/kg)	Laricitrin-IDROLISIACID/HPLC-UV- mg/kg laricitri
PETUNIDINE MONOGLUCOSID E (mg/kg) 3-	Pt-3-Glc-EST/HPLC-UV/VIS- mg/kg MV- 3-GLC chloride
CAMPFEROL (mg/kg)	Campferol-ACID HYDROLISIS/HPLC-UV- mg/kg campferol
PEONIDINE MONOGLUCOSID E (mg/kg) 3-	Po-3-Glc-EST/HPLC-UV/VIS- mg/kg MV- 3-GLC chloride
ISORAMNETINE (mg/kg)	Isoramnetin-IDROLISIS ACIDA/HPLC-UV- mg/kg isoramne
MALVIDIN MONOGLUCOSID E (mg/kg) 3-	Mv-3-Glc-EST/HPLC-UV/VIS- mg/kg MV- 3-GLC chloride

ASHES (%)	Ash-GRAV-%
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DELPHINIDIN MONOGLUCOSIDE ACILATE (mg/kg)	Dp-3-Glc-Acil-EST/HPLC-UV/VIS- mg/kgMV-3-GLCchloride
SYRINGETIN (mg/kg)	Syringetin- ACIDA/HPLC- HYDROLISIS UV- mg/kg syringeti
CYANIDIN MONOGLUCOSIDE ACILATE (mg/kg)	Cy-3-Glc-Acil-EST/HPLC-UV/VIS- mg/kgMV-3-GLCchloride
GRADE BRIX (°)	Grade Brix-RIFRAT-°
PETUNIDINE MONOGLUCOSIDE ACILATE (mg/kg)	Pt-3-Glc-Acil-EST/HPLC-UV/VIS- mg/kgMV-3-GLCchloride
PEONIDINE MONOGLUCOSIDE ACILATE (mg/kg)	Po-3-Glc-Acil-EST/HPLC-UV/VIS- mg/kgMV-3-GLCchloride
MALVIDIN MONOGLUCOSIDE ACILATE (mg/kg)	Mv-3-Glc-Acil-EST/HPLC-UV/VIS- mg/kgMV-3-GLCchloride
DELPHINIDIN MONOGLUCOSIDE CUMARATAE(mg/ kg)	Dp-3-Glc-P-Cum-EST/HPLC-UV/VIS- mg/kgMV-3-GLCchlorur
CYANIDIN MONOGLUCOSIDE CUMARATE (mg/kg)	Cy-3-Glc-P-Cum-EST/HPLC-UV/VIS- mg/kgMV-3-GLCchlorur
PETUNIDINE MONOGLUCOSIDE CUMARATE (mg/kg)	Pt-3-Glc-P-Cum-EST/HPLC-UV/VIS- mg/kgMV-3-GLCchlorur

PEONIDINE MONOGLUCOSIDE CUMARATE (mg/kg)	Po-3-Glc-P-Cum-EST/HPLC-UV/VIS- mg/kgMV-3-GLCchlorur
MALVIDIN MONOGLUCOSIDE CUMARATE (mg/kg)	Mv-3-Glc-P-Cum-EST/HPLC-UV/VIS- mg/kgMV-3-GLCchlorur

Table 1 List of analyses performed

Below are the results of the analyses performed on the apple pomace as is (Table 2).

LARICITRINE (mg/kg)	2,10
PETUNIDINE 3- MONOGLUCOSIDE (mg/kg)	<0.01
CAMPFEROL (mg/kg)	0,22
PEONIDINE 3- MONOGLUCOSIDE (mg/kg)	<0.01
ISORAMNETINE (mg/kg)	<0.1
MALVIDIN 3- MONOGLUCOSIDE (mg/kg)	<0.01
ASHES (%)	3,15
DELPHINIDIN 3- MONOGLUCOSIDE ACILATE (mg/kg)	<0.01
SYRINGETIN (mg/kg)	0,20

CYANIDIN MONOGLUCOSIDE ACILATE (mg/kg)	3-	<0.01
GRADE BRIX (°)		11,96
PETUNIDINE MONOGLUCOSIDE ACILATE (mg/kg)	3-	<0.01
PEONIDINE MONOGLUCOSIDE ACILATE (mg/kg)	3-	<0.01
MALVIDIN MONOGLUCOSIDE ACILATE (mg/kg)	3-	<0.01
DELPHINIDIN MONOGLUCOSIDE p- CUMARATE (mg/kg)	3-	<0.01
CIANIDIN MONOGLUCOSIDE p- CUMARATE (mg/kg)	3-	<0.01
PETUNIDIN MONOGLUCOSIDE p- CUMARATE (mg/kg)	3-	<0.01
PEONIDINE MONOGLUCOSIDE p- CUMARATE (mg/kg)	3-	<0.01
MALVIDINE MONOGLUCOSIDE p- CUMARATE (mg/kg)	3-	<0.01

Table 2 Results of analysis of apple pomace as it.

As can be seen from the table above, apple pomace is rich in antioxidants and total polyphenols and has higher concentrations of phloretin and luteolin, in particular.

Coffee waste and by-products (spent coffee grounds)

a) Food waste/by-product: During roasting process a complex series of chemical reactions takes place involving the different classes of compounds present in coffee beans (carbohydrates, lipids, proteins, amino acids, chlorogenic acids, alkaloids, etc.). Considering the polyphenols in coffee (especially chlorogenic acids), several studies show that the roasting process leads to a partial destruction of some of the chlorogenic acids present within the beans, while some fractions of chlorogenic acid derived from caffeic acid, ferulic acid and quinic acid remain in esterified forms within the beans. Both domestic extraction and industrial instantiation result in extraction of chlorogenic acids of up to 85-100%: a 200 mL cup of Arabica can therefore provide 70 to 200 mg of chlorogenic acids, while an identical amount of Robusta ranges from 70 to 300/350 mg of chlorogenic acids. In the case of the industrial production process of instant coffee, for every 1 kg of soluble coffee extracted, about 2 kg of coffee grounds are obtained with a total of more than 6 million tonnes of coffee grounds each year. The chemical composition varies from plant to plant according to different geographical locations, age, climate and soil conditions, but in general, coffee grounds are still rich in sugars, such as mannose and galactose, have a significant fraction of proteins and lipids, and contain high doses of caffeine, tannins and polyphenols, especially phenols and chlorogenic acid.

b) Processing considered for the matrix: Steam explosion proves to be an effective treatment for extracting the following compounds from spent coffee waste

- chlorogenic acids (up to 37.5% of the initial waste content)
- caffeine (up to 51% of the initial waste content)
- Polyphenols (up to 20% of the initial waste content)
- Fatty acids (up to 67% of the initial waste content)
- Sugars (100% extraction yield)

Then, to purify the substances, it is necessary to carry out an initial filtration at 50 μm . This is followed by a microfiltration process and nanofiltration to concentrate certain substances of interest (chlorogenic and coumaric acids, caffeine and polyphenols).

c) Outcome: The characterisation of the sample (spent coffee grounds) was carried out to assess:

- Total polyphenols and antioxidant capacity
- Ash, fibre, moisture, protein, fat, sugar, caffeine, chlorogenic acids
- Linoleic acid, oleic acid, palmitic acid, stearic acid

The results of the analysis are as follows:

- Total polyphenols, antioxidant capacity, flavonoids and anthocyanin profile

Active ingredient	Result		u.m.
Total polyphenols*	47.84	42.42	mg/ g dry weight gallic acid
Antioxidant capacity*	35.67	36.08	mg/ g dry weight ascorbic acid
Anthocyanins*	0.28	0.19	mg/ g dry weight malvidin-o-glucoside
Flavonoids	161.52		µg/ g dry weight quercetin

*tests carried out in duplicate

- Ash, fibre, moisture, protein, fat, sugar, caffeine, chlorogenic acids

Active ingredient	Result	u.m.
Dietary fibre	41.13	g/100 g dry

		weight
Fats	10,82	g/100 g dry weight
Humidity	53.8	g/100 g dry weight
Ashes	1.69	g/100 g dry weight
Caffeine	0.9	g/100 g dry weight
Protein	17.32	g/100 g dry weight
Soluble sugars	6.49	g/100 g dry weight
Chlorogenic acids (caffeic+ferulic+P-Coumaric)	6.06	g/100 g dry weight

- Linoleic acid, oleic acid, palmitic acid, stearic acid

Active ingredient	Result	u.m.
Linoleic Acid	5.04	g/100 g dry weight
Oleic acid	0.97	g/100 g dry weight

Palmitic Acid	0.84	g/100 g dry weight
Stearic Acid	3.92	g/100 g dry weight
Total fatty acids	10.78	g/100 g dry weight

As shown in the tables above, coffee pose still has a fair content of caffeine and total polyphenols, as well as chlorogenic acid and some long-chain fatty acids, particularly linoleic. According to these results spent coffee grounds can be considered a very interesting waste matrix for valorization.

Tomato processing by-products

a) Food waste/by-product: Tomatoes are rich in lycopene, phenolics, organic acids, vitamins and many other beneficial components. The tomato-processing by-product, also known as tomato pomace, consists of peel and seed (it represents around 4% of the fruit weight around 4% of the fruit weight) and is an excellent source of nutritional and nutraceutical substances useful to humans and of interest to the food industry. The consumption of tomatoes and tomato by-products decreases the risks of chronic and cardiovascular diseases (Song et al., 2017) and cancer. The most interesting component of the tomato is certainly its antioxidants:

- vitamin C (160-240 mg/kg);
- provitamin A (6-9 mg/kg, including β -carotene);
- vitamin E (5-20 mg/kg);
- phenolic compounds including flavonoids (5-50 mg/kg) and phenolic acids (10 50 g/kg)

b) Processing considered for the matrix: Tomato peels, waste from processing for the

production of sauces and concentrates, have been chemically characterized and show interesting concentrations of the following compounds: polyphenols, anthocyanins, flavonoids, carotenoids, lutein, lycopene. The treatments considered for the extraction of these substances are enzymatic hydrolysis and steam explosion processes. For the purification of the extracted substances the processes considered are solid-liquid separation by centrifugation and subsequent sequential separation of the molecules through tangential filtration processes. The process selected as optimal for the extraction of the substances of interest is steam explosion in combination with the centrifugation process and subsequent filtration on ceramic microfiltration membranes followed by ultrafiltration on the permeate of the microfiltration with polymeric membranes

c) Outcome: Tomato peels were chemically characterised for the evaluation of the concentration of the main compounds of interest. Since the peel production phase is confined exclusively to the summer period, it was decided to evaluate two different storage methods:

- storage at -20°C in a freezer; both on the sample as such and on subsequent hydrolysed and purified samples;
- use of a preservative, Potassium Sorbate (dosage 2 gr/kg) normally used in the food industry, to preserve the sample as such and subsequent hydrolysed and purified samples, evaluating its efficacy and possible interference with the analytical protocols used for analysis.

The characterisation of tomato peelings was carried out by evaluating the following parameters:

- antioxidant activity;
- quantification of polyphenols
- anthocyanins (UV/vis)
- flavonoids (UV/vis)
- carotenoids (HPLC method)
- lutein (HPLC method)
- glycopene (HPLC method)

Antioxidant activity		mg VEAC/ml on 100 gr tomato peels		
	Aug	Sept		
		rt	4°C	- 20°C
US	47,1		187,01	178,73
US'	56,5	195,98	187,36	240,20

Total polyphenols		mg gallic acid/ml on 100 gr tomato peels		
	Aug	Sept		
		rt	4°C	- 20°C
US	8,92		8,86	6,17
US'	8,73	11,45	7,41	9,22

Anthocyanins		mg malvidine-o-glucoside/ml on 100 gr tomato peels		
	Aug	Sept		
		rt	4°C	- 20°C
US	nd		4,88	3,90
US'	nd	5,89	2,31	3,77

Flavonoids		mg quercetin/ml on 100 gr tomato peels		
	Aug	Sept		
		rt	4°C	- 20°C
US	3,14		7,43	3,90
US'	2,65	10,86	3,44	3,77

HPLC			
	Concentration (total mg on 100 gr tomato peels)		
	Lutein	Lycopen 474 nm	Beta Carotene
US	0,00	0,87	0,00
US'	0,00	0,85	0,00

UNITO

Soybean hulls

a) Food waste/by-product: Italy is one of the main soy producers in Europe. With a global production of around 396 million Metric Tons (source: US Department of Agriculture), soy is a globally widespread crop widely used for the production of food, feed, medical products and for several industrial applications. Soybean hulls represent one the main by-products of soy processing (about 8-10%) and their main employments are for production of feeds, dietary fibers, ethanol, microfibril, bio-oil, herbal medicine. Since hulls contains a huge amount of cellulose and other biopolymers, new valorisation strategies could have an high economic and environmental impact.

b) Processing considered for the matrix: Two main valorisation strategy have been considered for this matrix: recovery of soybean peroxidase and cellulose isolation. The first process consists in buffer mediated enzyme extraction, followed by ultrafiltration and concentration steps and a final ionic exchange chromatographic purification. The second process has been firstly optimized employing classic multi-hydrolytic cellulose isolation and, successively, by using greener strategy (sub-critic water microwave assisted extraction, enzymatic pre-treatment etc.).

c) Outcome: Focusing on the cellulose isolation from soybean hulls, both the final biomass of classic multi-hydrolytic process (Hy-Cell) and optimized microwave assisted process (MW-Cell) have been characterized as well as the pristine hulls. The starting biomass percentage composition (5% Lipids, 49% Hemicellulose, 42% Cellulose, 4% Lignin) can be enriched in cellulose content in both the optimized developed processes (88% Hy-Cell and 91% MW-Cell). The comparison between the two strategies in terms of yield, cellulose quality, process selectivity and environmental metrics is still ongoing and LCA analysis will be carried out.

Rice husks

a) Food waste/by-product: Rice husks represent a diffuse agricultural waste, produced by the rice cultivation in Piedmont and Lombardy. Rice husks contain 15–20 wt% of silica in hydrated amorphous forms, depending on the variety, climate, and geographic location of production, and represent a safer, less expensive, and more environmentally friendly silica precursor with respect to commonly employed alkoxysilane compounds.

b) Processing considered for the matrix: SiO₂ might be obtained from rice husks by several different procedures, such as thermal/hydrothermal treatments, chemical attacks,

or biological digestion. We focus our attention on nitric acid digestion, that permits the extraction of amorphous SiO_2 .

c) Outcome: The characterization has been thoroughly carried out on all the matrices by means of many experimental techniques to find out qualitative and quantitative information about the relation between composition and structure of the valorized matrices. In particular powder-XRD diffraction and vibrational spectroscopies were used for structural characterization, electron microscopies (SEM, TEM) to investigate the morphology, EDS and inductively coupled plasma atomic emission spectroscopy for elements analysis. Results indicate that pure amorphous silica NPs are obtained by acid digestion.

Eggshells

a) Food waste/by-product: About 65.5 million metric tons of eggs are produced annually worldwide, and eggshells represent a common and diffuse waste. Eggshells are composed of approximately 94% of CaCO_3 and can be converted into different Ca-precursors to obtain hydroxyapatite.

b) Processing considered for the matrix: For eggshell, most of the studies in the literature involved a preliminary thermal treatment that convert eggshells in CaO. In our research hydroxyapatite was obtained by wet-precipitation method, dissolving eggshells in acid solution. Nitric acid and ascorbic acid were tested in the preparation. A part of the research has been devoted to the preparation of self-assembled nanocomposites starting from the above matrices with other substances coming from the valorization of urban waste (i.e., humic acids)

c) Outcome: Different experimental techniques were used to find out both the complete characterization and morphology information about this matrix. Structural characterization was obtained by PXRD and vibrational spectroscopies, together with electron microscopies (SEM, TEM). EDS and inductively coupled plasma atomic emission spectroscopy were used to analyze the elements composition of the samples. Hydroxyapatite nanoparticles suitable for further absorption of humic acids can be also obtained.

RICE BRAN

a) Food waste/by-product: Rice is one of the most important food crops in the world, representing a huge contribution to the dietary need of the global population. After cereal harvesting, rice is subjected to several milling processes to remove hull, germ, and bran and produce the final white rice. Bran is an external cereal layer, one of the most attractive rice by-products, representing around 9% of the cereal total weight. It contains proteins, dietary fibers, minerals, and lipids. One of the most common rice bran applications is the extraction of rice bran oil, rich in γ -oryzanol, which has shown many health benefits including antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, and anti-hypercholesterolemic properties.

b) Processing considered for the matrix: The analysis of the proximate composition was conducted to characterize the rice bran. Proximate composition in food matrices includes the determination of protein, lipid, carbohydrate, moisture, and ash contents. Rice bran oil is usually extracted by organic solvents, which are toxic for health and the environment. It would be interesting to explore the possibility of extracting this oil using innovative techniques such as ultrasound, microwaves, or enzymes to minimize the use of high amounts of organic solvents.

c) Outcome: The proximate composition in food matrices includes the determination of protein, lipid, carbohydrate, moisture and ash contents. The determination of total proteins was conducted following the "ISO 16634-1:2008", while the determination of total lipids, moisture and ash contents was conducted following the "Rapporto ISTISAN 1996/34" and the total carbohydrate content was calculated by difference as suggested by FAO (1998).

Rice Bran		(g/100g)
Moisture		6.87±0.30
Aashes		10.79±0.3
Protein		0
Carbohydrates		45.5±4.7
Total fatty substances		20.59±4.7
		7
		8.13±0.49

APPLE POMACE

a) Food waste/by-product: In 2022, the European apple production amounted to about 12 million tonnes, according to the European Commission. Around 71% of these apples are consumed fresh, while approximately 20% undergo processing to create value-added products. Among these processed products, about 65% are turned into apple juice concentrate, while the rest are used in the production of various other items. Apple pomace is rich in phytonutrients like polyphenols, dietary fibers, fatty acids, and minerals, which have potential applications as active ingredients in cosmetic, nutraceutical, or pharmaceutical products.

b) Processing considered for the matrix: The analysis of the proximate composition was conducted to characterize the apple pomace. Proximate composition in food matrices includes the determination of protein, lipid, carbohydrate, moisture, and ash contents. Recent studies have suggested employing innovative technologies to enhance the yields of bioactive compounds and optimize extraction procedures, aiming to minimize the use of chemicals and energy consumption. Among the array of innovative techniques, ultrasound-assisted extraction (UAE) and microwave-assisted extraction (MAE) have been increasingly investigated for extracting polyphenols from apple pomace.

c) Outcome: The proximate composition in food matrices includes the determination of protein, lipid, carbohydrate, moisture and ash contents. The determination of total proteins was conducted following the "ISO 16634-1:2008", while the determination of total lipids, moisture and ash contents was conducted following the "Rapporto ISTISAN 1996/34" and the total carbohydrate content was calculated by difference as suggested by FAO (1998). All values are presented as percentages. Given that the analyses were carried out in triplicate, the reported values represent the mean across the three samples, with the standard deviation provided.

Proximate composition of Apple Pomace	Mean value (%)	±
Moisture content (% w/w, wet AP basis)	50,45	0,21
Proteins (% w/w, dry AP basis)	3,14	0,20
Carbohydrates (% w/w, dry AP basis)	42,63	0,311
Lipids (Lipid content (% w/w, dry AP basis)	1,75	0,05

Ashes (% w/w, dry AP basis)

2,09

0,05

COFFEE SILVER SKIN

a) Food waste/by-product: Coffee is the second most commonly traded commodities after crude oil and their derivatives. In the coffee production the pulp and the parchment of the beans are removed. The final product of this process is green bean, which is commonly still wrapped by a thin outer layer of the coffee beans, called coffee silverskin. During the roasting process, the coffee bean is exposed at a high temperature, causing the water contained in the beans to evaporate rapidly, and the silverskin detaches from the beans. Some researchers have investigated the potential of coffee silverskin, and reported that coffee silverskin can be used as a natural source of prebiotic ingredients, fibre and antioxidants.

b) Processing considered for the matrix: Traditional extraction techniques have been employed to extract bioactive compounds, but they have limitations that require addressing. One such limitation is the extended extraction duration, resulting in significant time and energy consumption. Among the array of innovative techniques, ultrasound-assisted extraction (UAE) and microwave-assisted extraction (MAE) have been increasingly investigated for extracting polyphenols and antioxidant from silver skin.

c) Outcome: The proximate composition in food matrices includes the determination of protein, lipid, carbohydrate, moisture and ash contents. The determination of total proteins was conducted following the "ISO 16634-1:2008", while the determination of total lipids, moisture and ash contents was conducted following the "Rapporto ISTISAN 1996/34" and the total carbohydrate content was calculated by difference as suggested by FAO (1998). All values are presented as percentages. Given that the analyses were carried out in triplicate, the reported values represent the mean across the three samples, with the standard deviation provided.

	%	Standard dev
Moisture content	1,59	0,06
Proteins	19,52	0,19
Carbohydrates	66,18	0,16

Lipids	4,55	0,83
Ashes	8,26	0,09

UPO.

BLUEBERRY POMACE

a) Food waste/by-product: Due to its nutritional composition, attractive taste, and multi-therapeutic value, this fruit is considered a perfect example of a healthy food. Blueberries are widely consumed as fresh fruit or in processed product forms such as jam and juice. Fresh blueberries remain the main market, but due to their seasonal availability, limited storage time, and highly perishable properties, processing products like juices represents a conventional way to extend consumption and avoid subsequent economic losses. The blueberry processing chain generates huge amounts of pomace containing pulp, skin, and seeds, high in nutrients and bioactive compounds that could be exploited in different industrial sectors. In fact, blueberry waste has been the topic of various studies due to its high level of natural antioxidants, especially anthocyanins and phenolic acids, and dietary fiber. The pulp contains approximately only 10% of the total phenolic compounds, whereas the skin and seeds contain 28-35% and 60-70%, respectively, making blueberry manufacturing by-products a great source of phenolic compounds.

b) Processing considered for the matrix: The proximate composition of blueberry pomace includes the determination of protein, lipid, simple sugars, total dietary fiber, oligosaccharides, moisture, and ash content. The growing interest in the exploitation of cell-wall hydrolyzing and carbohydrases has been introduced to release cell wall complex polyphenols and now is being expanded into dietary fiber-targeted applications to generate prebiotic oligosaccharides. Treating by-products rich in insoluble fiber using enzymes represents a sustainable strategy to obtain a functional ingredient rich in prebiotic oligosaccharides and bioaccessible phenolics, which can be used to fortify solid and liquid foods.

b) Outcome: The proximate composition in food matrices includes the determination of protein, lipid, sugars, total dietary fiber, oligosaccharides, moisture and ash contents. The analyses were carried out in triplicate, the reported values represent the mean across the three samples,

with the standard deviation provided. In addition to the dietary fiber-targeted enzymatic hydrolysis, it will be interesting to conduct an in-depth analysis of the lipidic fraction.

Parameter	Amount
Moisture (%)	45.49±0.67
Ashes (g/100 d.w.)	0.86±0.01
Fats (g/100 d.w.)	9.47±0.01
Protein (g/100 d.w.)	10.18±0.64
TDF (g/100 d.w.)	59.27±2.67
Oligosaccharides (g/100 d.w.)	0.68±0.01
GOS (g/100 d.w.)	0.16±0.01
FOS (g/100 d.w.)	0.52±0.01
Simple sugars (g/100 d.w.)	7.43±0,01
Sucrose (g/100 d.w.)	0.03±0.00
Fructose (g/100 d.w.)	3.5±0.01
Glucose (g/100 d.w.)	3.9±0.01

COCOA BEAN SHELLS

a) Food waste/by-product:

Cocoa bean shells (CBSs) represent the external layer of cocoa beans. The shells are removed during the winnowing, a

processing step of chocolate production, and they are considered a waste material. About 700 thousand tonnes every year of CBSs are produced, specifically during the roasting phase when bean shells are de-hulled from the rest of the bean and discarded. CBSs are characterized by a significant dietary fibre (DF) content, up to 59% of the dry weight. CBSs were kindly provided by an Italian leader chocolate producer. The cocoa bean shells (CBS) are Nacional variety originating from Ecuador. The sample is composed of cocoa bean shells, recovered after the winnowing process, during the production of chocolate-based products.

b) Processing considered for the matrix: Enzyme-driven valorization was selected to up-cycle cocoa bean shells, previously characterized in their high pectin content, as well as the polyphenolic content, particularly focusing on clovamide antioxidant compound. Preliminary enzymatic treatments have been performed for CBSs and defatted CBSs using cellulase, xylanase and pectinase in different combinations. Preliminary results

showed that the enzymatic treatment was effective in enhancing soluble fibers of CBSs, which are potentially associated with fermentability and prebiotic activity on human gut microbiota, and a parallel conservation of almost the entire antioxidant capacity after the treatments. Work on characterization of the sample is still ongoing.

- c) Outcome:** Proximate composition of our CBSs (Forastero variety from Ecuador, donated by an Italian chocolate producer) is showed in table 1. Data suggest that our samples are perfectly in line with those reported in the literature with a very high percentage of SDF.

Parameter	Amount
Moisture (%)	4,42±0,2
Ashes (g/100)	7,76±0,02
Fats (g/100)	8,04±0,01
Protein (g/100)	10,5±0,42
Carbohydrates (g/100)	11,13±0,86
TDF (g/100)	58,14±1,11
IDF (g/100)	42,22±0,59
SDF (g/100)	15,91±0,51

Table 1. Proximate composition; Total Dietary Fiber, TDF; Insoluble Dietary Fiber, IDF; Soluble

The use of different combination of enzymes (Class 3, hydrolases) permitted to increase the fraction of soluble fiber (even if in very small percentage), improving the prebiotic capacity of the matrix. The evaluation of the textural properties of this new valorized (and depolyphenolized/defatted) fiber is ongoing.

COW MILK WHEY

- a) Food waste/by-product:** Due to the very large quantity of cow whey production, this matrices could be considered a significant sources of minor bioactive compounds (e.g. cow milk prebiotic oligosaccharides and enzymes like lactoferrin). The recovery of whey from cheesemaking is easy to be obtained, and beside the “classical” recovery of whey proteins

and lactose, more strategies to valorize the aqueous phase as well as the minor bioactive compounds could be made, in order to valorize this matrix.

- b) Processing considered for the matrix:** the samples of the cow milk whey were recovered from cheesemaking and processed first by microfiltration, then by ultrafiltration (polysulfone membrane, 20 KDa). The retentate (VCF: 2) was first analyzed in order to evaluate the protein profile using 2D electrophoresis, confirming the presence of major and minor proteins. Moreover, the permeate was characterized in order to evaluate its prebiotic capacity, considering some probiotic strains (*Lactobacillaceae*). Moreover, a preliminary fermentation using *Lactobacillus* spp were done in order to valorize the matrix (production of postbiotics).
- c) Outcome:** The bi-dimensional analysis of the protein fraction on concentrated whey confirmed the presence of minor bioactive proteins (lactoferrin; lactoperoxidase) in the material. More investigation are now ongoing in order to characterize minor compounds in permeate, with the final aim to obtain a oligosaccharides-rich fraction added by partially concentrated lactoferrin.

Moreover, the permeate showed a boosting capacity to stimulate the growth of probiotic

strains, when compared with conventional media, as reported for *B. infantis*:

APPLE POMACE

a) Food waste/by products

Apple is one of the most widely consumed fruits worldwide, both as fresh and processed. During industrial processing only one part, the pulp, is recovered for the production of juices, jams and extracts, while peel, seeds, stem and even discarded apples represent waste materials despite the fact that the nutrition of these products is favourable; this waste is composed by peels, cores and seeds, and it is a significant part (30%) of the total weight of the fruit. Apple by-products is commonly used as animal feed and biofuel, but it is an important source of polyphenols and dietary fiber. Among polyphenols, phloretin and phlorizin are considered a natural strategy to modulate glucose in the blood, so reducing the blood glycemia.

b) Processing considered for the matrix: this by-product will undergo some processes to improve the extraction of bioactive compounds. Among these processes, ultrasound treatment (US) for the extraction intensification has been considered, also in the combination with enzymes (or with fermentation with probiotic strains, ongoing activity). After these treatments the characterization of bioactive compounds and fiber has been evaluated. Furthermore a green extraction with subcritical water and the characterisation of these

aqueous extract will be done, particularly exploiting the parallel work of the academic POC GREENVAL (UPO, NODES).

c) Outcome: Apple pomace has been kindly provided by an Italian company, and its proximate composition has been done. The main results are shown in Tab.1.

Parameter	Amount
Moisture (%)	75.98 ± 1.02
Ashes (% d.w.)	1.72 ± 0.01
Protein (% d.w.)	3.76 ± 0.34
Fats (% d.w.)	5.20 ± 1.16
TDF (% d.w.)	59.24 ± 0.78

Table 1: proximate composition; total dietary fiber (TDF).

It can be seen from the results that the fiber content has a high value, around 59%. This raw material therefore could be a good source of fiber and the results are in line with those reported in literature. In fact, the fiber derived from this by-product is often added in bakery products because of its high pectin content.

Furthermore, the content of bioactive compounds has been evaluated, in particular the total phenolic content (TPC) with the method of Folin Ciocalteu; also the antioxidant activity (DPPH method) has been investigated. Data are reported in Tab. 2.

Parameter	Amount
-----------	--------

TPC (% d.w.)	0.21 ± 0.01
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Table 2: total phenolic compound (TPC)

RICE BYPRODUCTS: HUSK AND BRAN

- a) Food waste/by-product:** Among the cereal grains, rice (*Oryza sativa* L.) represents one of the most important human food crops consumed in the world. Based on FAO's estimates for global cereal production, 517 million tons of milled rice were produced in 2022 (FAO, 2023). Rice is commonly consumed as milled rice, which is initially produced by removing the husk from the paddy to obtain unpolished rice and then removing the bran during the milling process. However, the subsequent removal of the outer bran layers from unpolished rice, which consist of the pericarp, aleurone, sub-aleurone layer, and germ, results in a loss of sensorial properties and beneficial nutrients. Rice bran, the principal edible by-product obtained from rice processing, has recently gained interest due to its high dietary fiber and protein content as well as bioactive components such as polyphenols, gamma-oryzanol, and tocopherols. Contrary to the large characterization of brain oil and gamma oryzanol, the fiber fraction was less investigated, even if some application "as it" as commonly used (also regarding its use in material like cement).
- b) Processing considered for the matrix:** The proximate composition of rice husk and bran includes the determination of protein, total dietary fiber, moisture, and ash content. Dry sieving after rice seeds processing was considered. Enzyme-driven treatment for the enrichment of the fiber soluble fraction is ongoing, considering different pool of enzymes (class 3 hydrolases; carbohydrases). Moreover, the bioactivity of these fiber-rich and polyphenol-rich by-products was assessed, quantifying the total phenolic content and the antioxidant activity (DPPH[•] method).
- c) Outcome:** These findings underscore the potential health benefits associated with the external layers of the caryopsis, often wasted, rich in phenolic compounds and fiber, which could be crucial for developing functional foods and bioactive ingredients with enhanced antioxidant properties. The concentration of phenolic constituents and the resulting antioxidant activity were found in greater amounts in the bran.

Parameters	Husk	Bran
Moisture (%)	7.84±0.45	8.77±0.39
Ashes (g/100 d.w.)	15.63±0.32	8.64±0.17
Protein (g/100 d.w.)	2.05±0.14	13.48±0.21
TDF (g/100 d.w.)	73.99±2.4 5	27.97±0.52
Antioxidant capacity (mmol TE/Kg d.w.)	6.54±0.57	64.59±7.9 6
Total polyphenols (mg CE/g d.w.)	3.60±0.12	7.75±0.28

On the other hand, rice husk contains approximately 75% organic matter, principally dietary fiber, and rest mineral components such as silica and trace elements, making it exploitable in the building industries and domestic fields. The valorization of the dietary fiber using other technological approaches (e.g. steam extraction coupled with enzyme-driven hydrolysis could be a strategy to intensify the extraction as well as to produce new fibers and oligosaccharides with bioactive (nutraceutical and pharma areas) and texturizing properties (food area).

OILS FROM FRUIT SEEDS COLD-PRESSING

a) Food waste/by-product: Plant edible oils can be prepared using different approaches: the cold-pressing method (hydraulic- or strew-pressing process) is largely used in order to recover oils from seeds and kernels. Apricot (*P. armeniaca*) and peach (*P. persica*) cold-pressed oils from kernels are interesting principally because of their composition and their flavouring volatile fraction, but also relating to their potential functional properties, despite their high cost and the difficulty to prepare the kernels for the extraction from the seeds. Plant edible oils are often an important source of food for humans, because they provide essential fatty acids and minor bioactive compounds (e.g., tocopherols). Moreover, they could be used in cosmetic and pharmaceutical applications

also due to their anti-microbial, anti-septic, anti-oxidant properties, as well as considered “gourmet” oils in food market. The cold-pressing process (depending on the processing parameters and the temperature reached during the production) usually preserve the nutritional quality of the oils, representing an elective method for lipid extraction from food matrices. Apricot and peach cold-pressed seed oils are remarkable principally because of their composition and their volatile flavoring fraction, but also relating to their potential functional properties, despite their high cost and the difficulty to prepare the kernels for the seeds extraction. The principal aim of this work has been the production of oils samples from apricot and peach, comparing cold-pressing appositely produced for the study with some commercial samples, obtained from solvent extraction.

b) Processing considered for the matrix:

Oils were produced by cold-pressing, following the seeds recovery. An expeller model of press was used to extract oil from the matrix.

This preliminary study lead to obtain i) their fatty acids composition ii) cyanogenic glycosides content. The thermal impact evaluated by TGA (Thermo-Gravimetric Analysis) characterization is ongoing.

Analytical methods:

Analysis of fatty acid (FA) composition: the fatty acids in the lipid fraction were transesterified into the corresponding methyl esters (FAMES), then analyzed by GC-FID.

Cyanogenic glycosides presence: the analysis of these components was performed using a UHPLC- HRMS Thermo QExactive (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Waltham, USA).

HS-SPME-GC-MS was used in order to evaluate the volatile profile (ongoing) and the potential presence of acrolein.

c) Outcome:

The Fatty acids profile is decisive for the quality of the oil. We identified 14 and 12 fatty acids in peach oil and apricot cold pressed oils, respectively, of which oleic, linoleic, palmitic and stearic acids were found to be the most relevant (Tab.1).

	NPO	NAO
C18:1n-9cis	70.60 ± 0.08	66.01 ± 0.05
C18:2n-6cis	21.41 ± 0.01	26.32 ± 0.03
C16:0	5.32 ± 0.09	5.15 ± 0.09
C18:0	1.45 ± 0.01	1.18 ± 0.01

Tab.1 More abundant FA in peach kernel oil and apricot seed oil (relative percentage; triplicate; average \pm standard deviation).

The parallel extraction (Soxhlet apparatus) of lipid fraction from raw seeds used to produce oils, permitted to confirm the same trend for fatty acids composition (no significant differences were found, when compared to those obtained by cold pressed oils).

The HS-SPME-GC-MS analysis of commercial apricot and peach oil confirmed the presence of acrolein in trace (Tab. 2), depending on a probable thermal degradative process, when compared to cold-pressed oils.

Tab. 2 Comparison between non-commercial and commercial AO and PO made by HS-SPME-GC-MS. Analyses were performed in triplicate; results are expressed as mean \pm standard deviation, in mg/kg of the molecules used for the quantitation of that VOC. nd: not detected.

VOLATILE COMPOUND	<i>Prunus armeniaca</i> L.		<i>Prunus persica</i> L.	
	Non-commercial	Commercial	Non-commercial	Commercial
Acrolein (2-propenal)	nd	0.358 \pm 0.059	nd	0.097 \pm 0.003
Benzaldehyde	5.953 \pm 0.154	0.013 \pm 0.001	16.370 \pm 0.905	0.010 \pm 0.001
Benzyl acetate	4.800 \pm 0.426	nd	1.770 \pm 0.077	nd
Benzyl alcohol	1.983 \pm 0.132	nd	1.412 \pm 0.051	nd

This difference has been also confirmed by TGA analysis (ongoing analysis, data not reported), which highlighted the low stability of the commercial samples, probably extracted with solvent or de-odorized. Finally, traces of cyanogenic glycosides (concentration lower than legal limit: 20 mg/Kg in apricot seeds, not processed or ground) were found in both cold-pressed oils (HCN: 0,286 and 0,154 mg/Kg fresh weight, for peach and apricot oils, respectively), whereas the commercial oils do not have these compounds, also in this case probably as a result of refining processes.

All these findings support well the production and the use of these high value oil in pharma, cosmetic and nutraceutical areas.

Final considerations and perspectives

The activity here described was primarily directed **to identify the best performing material useful to be scaled up at pilot level, producing new valorized materials useful in different applications (pharma , nutraceuticals, food, cosmetic, agronomic areas).**

The selection of the material was done also considering the chance to share some materials within the Partners, in a collaborative interdisciplinary vision, as well as exploiting and different technologies on the same raw material. This activity will be planned considering the structures and the facilities present in the various academic Departments, as well as considering some facilities potentially available depending on the collaborations of each Partners with Companies already identified and/or involved in cascade corporate POC projects within NODES.

Following an extensive debate about the matrices, considering the main results obtained and the common interests, **4 principal areas of intervention/matrices were identified:**

- i. whey/buttermilk/waste fractions from UF of milk**
- ii. rice waste (husk, chaff, straw)**
- iii. nerve waste (spent coffee; roasted cocoa peel)**
- iv. apple pressing waste.**

It is planned to work on the valorisation of the above matrices by exploiting combined and synergistic "green" and "bio-based" techniques, tested in the first part of the activity, as synthetically described in this Deliverable, optimizing a series of processes that will lead to the selection of - at least - 3 scalable and sustainable processes, both in terms of product and process availability, as planned in the RM2_GRIP. It will be a matter of obtaining sufficient quantities of material to test a "model" production of functional foods/food supplements/cosmetics, as well as obtaining quantities of molecules of added high-value that will be characterized as well as used in the various sectors (including phyto-stimulation and production of porous materials useful to remove environmental contaminants, particularly considering the material obtained from rice waste).

The different research units will be able to work on the different matrices by sharing technologies and skills, although it is not necessary for all the units to work on all the matrices. It will be essential to obtain at least 2 types of "valued product" per raw matrix, so allowing the selection of at least 3 "scalable" processes at a pre-competitive pilot level.

Main expected results:

I. "Milk" area:

biocatalysis for the production of bioactive compounds containing galactose (surfactants, characterized by transversal marketability, with potential in cosmetic and other applications; characterization of concentrated fractions rich in prebiotic oligosaccharides and lactoferrin useful in nutraceutical applications). The whey/buttermilk matrices can be also transferred to the RM4 works, for microalgal biomass production tests).

ii. Rice waste area:

texturizing fibres; prebiotic oligosaccharides; porous materials (in the case of rice bran lipids - solidifiable lipids); antioxidant/anti-inflammatory polyphenols

iii. "Nervine" waste (spent coffee; roasted cocoa bean husks):

texturizing fibres; prebiotic oligosaccharides; chlorogenic acids; methylxanthine; proteins, medium chain fatty acids, polyphenols

iv. Apple pomace:

fibre, pectin, phlorizin/phloretin, bioactive antioxidant polyphenols, new media for probiotic bacteria growth.